

Digital Information Access and Ideological Education: The Impact of Library Platforms on Student Worldview Formation

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Abstract

The ideological education is rapidly changing in the global economy with the purpose is to give strength to the morality and to cultivate the people. The principal objective of this study is to give quantitative layout to the student's worldview formation (SWF) in a unique trend by adding the digital information access as a regressor of SWF with the addition of library platform as mediator and ideological education as a moderator. Initially, the questionnaire development has gone through both pretesting and pilot testing procedures with the quantitative confirmation through Cronbach alpha as reliability instrument. The final data collection starts with 500 questionnaires, out of which 368 were finally found as statistically valid, showing 73 percent of the response rate. The results use the frequency distribution to expand every single feedback from the respondents, giving a novel insight to the readers. Additionally, results confirm a boost in the student world view formation through digital information access, strongly moderated and mediated by ideological education and library platform.

Keywords: Digital Information, Ideological Education, Library Platform, Student Worldview Formation.

Introduction

In this paper, a frequency-based analysis was

conducted to expose the views of the respondents in regarded to their views about the digital information access and ideological education. It further explored the library platforms as mediating variable and ideological education as the moderator between the digital information access and Student Worldview Formation. In the modern days, the advancement in the technology and information provides an outlook to a new domain named as digital information. Digitalization is the process of converting the information from analog to digital. When a paper report is converting into digital form like pdf, the data does not change but it is converted into digital format. Digitalization is based on the digitized information by using the digital technology to simply transform the reporting process (Pellicelli, 2023). Digital information is that type of the information which is stored, manipulated and displayed by computational tools (Khosrow-Pour, 2005). Digital information access (DIA) is simply the ability to obtain, retrieve and utilize the information with the help of digital mediums like internet, digital databases, e-books, multimedia content, online journals, and repositories. It involves a vast array of data and information being accessed through technological resources. The significance of university students lies in their pivotal role as the future leaders (Igbal et al., 2023). As a result, they navigate through higher education, they acquire the knowledge, skills, and critical thinking abilities essential for addressing complex global challenges (Moustaghfir and Brigui, 2024). Moreover, university students are not only recipients of academic learning but also active contributors to research, innovation, and societal progress (Puente et al., 2021).

For providing a better sense and understanding,

it is the core duty of the educational professionals, and teachers to teach and shape the exposure of the students to various political, social and cultural ideologies. The basis is to focus on how the students think about the moral principles, social culture, and global issues which fosters critical thinking and understanding about the diverse perspective in the globalized world. This whole phenomenon is that ideological education and research pay a remarkable attention to this title. The literature also put more focus on the combined term of political and ideological education. It is a social practice in which a social group or a society uses some certain ideas, political views and concepts with the moral values to improve the ideology of the students. Therefore, such efforts generate ideological and moral qualities among the students to conform to social status quo (Jiang et al., 2019).

Library platform is a digital system or infrastructure that can provide access to various resources including the books, articles, journals, multimedia, databases and other scholarly materials (Wang and Li, 2021; Zhang et al., 2022). These platforms are offered by academic institutions including the universities, public libraries, and digital repositories (Jain, 2011; Plantin and Thomer, 2025). The key purpose of designing such platform is to facilitate the access, discovery and information management for the students, faculty members, researchers and other members (Habib et al., 2021). Moreover, library platform often includes the tools for managing the resources like citation management, digital storage,

and organizational feature, various library platform integrates with the learning management system, therefore, making it quite easier for the faculty and students to access educational resources. With the more engagement of the users with these platforms, they also improve their digital literacy. The LIP can mediate the relationship between the digital information access and student worldwide formation by serving as a major tool through which students can engage with digital resources. As the DIA provides better access to broad range of information, LIP facilitate the organized delivery and interaction with that information, therefore, enabling the students to explore the diverse perspective, cultures and ideologies.

In the current diverse and interconnected world, the student's worldview plays a critical role in shaping their personal and academic growth. This field of interest is well documented in the domain of student worldview formation. This refers to as the development of the overall perspective in the students about beliefs and understanding about the global views. However, this process is influenced by variety of factors like cultural exposure, educational experience, and social interaction. With the growing global trends, students encounter various perspectives and ideologies, they further refine their beliefs and understanding and become more aware about the social, political and cultural dynamics. Ultimately, SWF shapes how students approach critical thinking, engage with global challenges, and interact with diverse cultures and ideas. Based on the above background, Figure 1 demonstrates the model.

Figure 1: Study Model (Source: Researchers).

The remaining study is organized in several different sections, like the upcoming debate covers the theoretical context of the above-mentioned variables. Section 3 talks about methodology and analysis, and Section 4 provides results through frequency distribution and path analysis (direct,

moderation and mediation). Conclusion is provided in the Section 5.

Literature

This study adopts the method of literature

summary as presented using Table 1. The summary provides the variables of the observation and the sources from which the material has been extracted.

Table 1(a): Summary of the Past Related Studies.

No.	Study Focus (Region)	Variable	Materials/Methods	Key Results	Source/Reference
1	Digital scholarly environment (CIBER's Virtual Scholar Programme)	Information-seeking behaviour of students	Log data from digital journals libraries (Blackwell Synergy, OhioLINK) and e-book collection (Oxford Scholarship Online)	Students were the biggest users in terms of sessions and pages viewed, more likely to undertake longer online sessions. Undergraduates and postgraduates frequently used library links to access scholarly databases.	(Nicholas et al., 2009)
2	University students (1st & 3rd year)	Evaluation of trustworthiness of online health information	Questionnaire-based survey; Exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses	1st-year students identified 4 factors: ease of use, content, recommendation, and brand. 3rd-year students identified 7 factors: content, credibility, recommendation, ease of use, usefulness, style, and brand. 3rd-year students had a clearer evaluation process.	(Johnson et al., 2016)
3	Australian universities (Staff & Students)	Perceptions and use of current and emerging technologies	Interviews and focus groups with 46 first-year students and 31 staff from three universities	The study questions assumptions about the "digital divide" between "digital native" students and "digital immigrant" teachers. Findings suggest that both students and staff engage similarly with technology, and a more nuanced understanding is needed for technology implementation in higher education.	(Waycott et al., 2010)
4	ICT in Education (General)	Computer literacy and generational differences	Conceptual framework for analyzing ICT-supported teaching, focusing on digital natives vs. digital immigrants	The paper highlights the potential of internet search engines as unifying tools for digital natives and digital immigrants, promoting a shift from traditional ICT-supported teaching methods.	(Válek and Sládek, 2012)
5	Students' Use of Computers in Schools (Region unspecified)	Impact of technology on learning preferences	Surveys filled out by students from different schools (high school, middle school)	* Students with digital technology use in public schools felt they knew better than teachers. * No evidence of effective human-computer partnership for learning.	(Kolikant, 2009)
6	COVID-19 Pandemic (Global)	Student perceptions of online education and digital technologies	Bibliometric review combined with a systematic review of 154 articles from Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) databases.	* Students have a positive view of online education, valuing flexibility, digital technology, and self-directed learning. * Challenges include adapting to sudden shifts and ensuring quality and satisfaction.	(Cramarenco et al., 2023)
7	Gansu Agricultural University, China	University students' digital competence	Quantitative methodology; Survey technique; Non-experimental method	* Students had positive perceptions of digital competencies, particularly in information literacy, communication, and safety. * Significant differences in self-perceptions based on gender, grade, residence, and prior training. * Emphasizes the need for targeted training in digital content creation and ICT use.	(Zhao et al., 2021)
8	Non-enrollment in LIS Programs (Region unspecified)	Factors influencing non-enrollment in Library and Information Science programs	Survey of 537 students assessing perceptions of librarians and LIS programs	* Students perceive librarians as approachable and knowledgeable. * Lack of personal interest is the main barrier to enrolling in LIS programs. * Strong support for the importance of libraries and advocacy for increased funding and technology improvements.	(Adetayo et al., 2024)
9	Gansu Agricultural University, China	Perceptions of engineering librarian as instructor	Quantitative methodology; Survey technique	Engineering students positively perceived the librarian as an instructor in multimodal learning environments, although there was a recurring issue of limited access to technology.	(Omarsaib, 2023)

Table 1(b): Summary of the Past Related Studies.

No.	Study Focus (Region)	Variable	Materials/Methods	Key Results	Source/Reference
10	University Library Space Reimagining (Global)	Role of library space in modern learning environments	Case study approach; Examining library initiatives and projects	The shifting to a "library as platform" requires flexible management, new staff roles and skills. It emphasizes the need for libraries to support user-driven learning and creation.	(Andrews et al., 2016)
11	Pedagogical Conditions for Scientific Worldview Formation (Russia)	Role of biology teaching in shaping scientific worldview	Case study approach; Pedagogical diagnostics	The positive student perceptions of biology teaching as a tool for developing a scientific worldview.	(Kondaurova et al., 2020)
12	Role of Ideological Education in Formation of Worldviews (Global)	Moral vs. Amoral ideologies in education	Theoretical exploration	The study contrasts moral ideologies (promoting human agency) with amoral ideologies.	(Alexander, 2005)
13	Impact of Ideological and Political Education on Social Entrepreneurial Intention (China)	Impact of ideological education on social entrepreneurial intention	Survey of 447 university graduates; Regression analysis; Bootstrapping method	Ideological and political education positively impacts social entrepreneurial intention by enhancing prosocial motivation. Entrepreneurship education strengthens this effect.	(Alexander, 2005)
14	Virtual Reality in Ideological Education (China)	Impact of VR on ideological education	Empirical study using VR technology	The results show that VR technology enhances ideological and political education by immersing students in historical events and social practices.	(Bao and Xiao, 2026)
15	Ideological Education and Air Quality (China)	Impact of ideological education on urban air quality	Panel data from 100+ Chinese cities (2010–2023); Spatial econometric and mediation models	Ideological and political education positively influences social entrepreneurial intention by promoting prosocial motivation, which is mediated by online discussions. Public pressure and policy responses lead to significant environmental improvements.	(Li, 2025)
16	AI in Ideological Education (China)	Use of AI in enhancing ideological and political education	Empirical study on AI-driven educational methods	AI technologies, such as N-gram language models and unsupervised learning algorithms, enhance the effectiveness of ideological and political education by facilitating deeper content understanding and improving ideological development through NLP and image depth estimation.	(Shang, 2025)

Social Cognitive Theory

The theoretical view of the social cognitive theory (SCT) is captured through a framework that explains the functioning of humans through interaction with the environment, personal, and behavioural cognitive factors. This theory establishes the idea that these set of factors emphasize on observational learning, self regulation and self learning. There is a wider implication of SCT in the domain of information science research. A nominated study of Middleton et al. (2019) has a prime focus on this theory with the specific reference to information-seeking behaviour and knowledge sharing. The concept of digital information access objectifies how the information through digital channels is being collected and analyze. Nemati lafmejani et al. (2021a) use the cognitive theory to explain how the users' mental processes (personality), actions (behavior), and environment (system interface) influence their interaction with information. It further highlights how these factors shape the information of the users in retrieval and decision-making. Digital information access influences learning by providing students with diverse sources of knowledge, shaping their behaviours and cognitive processes.

The theory of SCT also justified for the digital libraries and related information sources. This is well documented by Nemati Lafmejani et al. (2021b). Their investigation focus is on the impact of Bandura's SCT on the interaction of the users with Iranian academic digital libraries. By using the structural equation modelling, results are favouring the assumption that these factors significantly affect users' interaction with digital libraries. The research underscores the importance of cognitive, behavioral, and environmental. In the last decade, Kim (2010) conduct a study about the intentions to use university library website resources through gender differences. The results confirms that male are more goal-oriented while female give the preference to user-friendly interface. This demonstrates how cognitive factors shape the way users engage with digital library resources.

Ideological education acts as a moderator by influencing the relationship between access to information (DIA) and worldview formation (SWF). It adds a layer of filtering, potentially reinforcing or altering how students process and interpret information based on their educational context. Taking the base from the stated theory, Zhao (2022) integrates the educational and cognitive psychology to explore the impact of the political and ideological education

on the college students. Using cognitive structure theory, it examines students' self-cognition and IPE, highlighting how opportunity and challenge factors significantly influence their Ideological and political educational strategies. Overall, the study justifies these variables by using the social cognitive theory. It is important to note that still there are several theoretical debates, focusing on this theory and the variables of this research (Gan et al., 2023; Guan et al., 2025; Wang and Shao, 2024).

Methodology

Variables, Measures, Pretesting and Pilot Testing

The study captures the digital information access as the main independent variable. It is defined as the ability of the individuals or groups to digital tools, technologies and resources to find and utilize online information. The main outcome variable is student worldwide formation means the global trends, pathways and other practices that support the international students in perusing their education. The main mediating variable is library platform is a core service platform which integrates different services provided by the library. It considers the resource sharing and cataloguing for both the staff, faculty members and students. Moreover, the study takes the student worldwide formation refers to the global formation of the students through cultural integration and epistemic transformation. It further determines the students' mobility under cross-boarders while developing global identity. The study has another variable named ideological education. This is the moderator between digital information access and student worldview formation nexus. SWF is the practice using different ideas, political views, and moral values to shape the students values and ideologies. The study uses self developed items for these variables which are described in section 4. Both the pre-testing and pilot testing procedures were applied. Under pre-testing, the developed questionnaire was presented to 2 experts. They have conducted a detailed review and give their valuable suggestions (as shown in the second last column of Table 2). All the suggestions are well incorporated and questionnaire was updated accordingly.

The pilot testing of the questionnaire, conducted with a sample of 50 respondents. It has yielded a

very satisfactory results with Cronbach's alpha. The values were ranging from 0.72 to 0.87 across the different variables. The Digital Information Access and Ideological Education variables exhibited strong internal consistency. These variables show the alpha

values of 0.85 as highest and lowest as 0.87, indicating reliable measurement. The Library Platforms variable demonstrated a slightly lower alpha of 0.75. It is suggesting a good room for improvement in some items.

Table 2: Expert Suggestions for Questionnaire Updates.

Variable	Type/Nature of Variable	Items For Measurement	Pre-Testing (Suggestions From Experts)	Pilot Testing (Cronbach Alpha)
Digital Information Access (DIA)	Independent	05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplify and clarify wording for better comprehension. Include additional questions to measure frequency of use and satisfaction. 	0.85
Library Platforms (LIP)	Mediator	03		0.75
Student Worldview Formation (SWF)	Dependent	05		0.72
Ideological Education (IDE)	Moderator	03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capture both active and passive engagement. Address barriers to access or usage. Assess content's impact on personal beliefs or perspectives.	0.85

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection procedure is a combination of several activities which are incorporated using the 5 team members. The starting phase is to equally distribute the 500 copies in each of the team members, covering 100 samples of questionnaire for each of the teammates. Next, the teammates have also distributed the targeted public and private universities from which the data was aimed to collect. After this, every single member had personally visited the assigned universities to collect the data through

convenient sampling technique from the students in different departments. After the time duration of 3.5 weeks, the team was able to collect back a total of 413 questionnaires. The remaining copies were not returned by the respondents. The collected copies were further investigated and found that there are 45 copies (413-368) are those with invalid filling by the respondents; therefore, dropped from the valid response. Our final sample is 368 questionnaires which shows 73% response rate: indeed, a good one for the analysis. The similar detail is captured in Table 3.

Table 3: Data Collection Procedure and Response Statistics.

Steps	Details	Number	Percentage
1. Distribution of Questionnaires	Questionnaires distributed to students from public and private universities	500	100%
2. Sampling Method	Convenient sampling technique applied	-	-
3. Team Assistance	6 members assisted in distribution, collection, and management	6	-
4. Collection and Review	Questionnaires returned and reviewed	413	82.6%
5. Final Sample Selection	Excluded incorrectly filled questionnaires	368	73.6%

Analysis Techniques

Two methods named frequency distribution and path analysis are applied. First, the frequency distribution was used to examine the distribution of responses across various questionnaire items. This is a good approach as it provides a clear picture of trends and patterns of the responses. This helped in understanding how respondents from different universities do the perception about the variables. Following this, path analysis was conducted to assess the relationships among the variables. This included direct analysis to determine the direct effects of digital information access to student worldview formation. The further analysis includes the moderation as well as the mediation analysis to explore how other

variables might influence or explain these relationships (i.e., digital information access-student worldview formation).

Results and Explanation

Frequency Analysis

Overall total number of participants of the study are 368 as shown in Table 4, out of which 48 are under 20 years of age, 81 in 20-25 years. The maximum respondents are 102 in the age range of 26-30. And 11% respondents belong to their age of above 35 years. 72% are the male members as participates, whereas mostly students belong to engineering field of study with a share of 42%.

Table 4(a): Demographics.

Age	Frequency	% Share
Under 20	48	13
20-25	81	22
26-30	102	28
31-35	98	27
Above 35	39	11
Total	368	100
Gender		
Male	265	72
Female	103	28
Total	368	100
Field of Study		
Humanities	19	5

Table 4(b): Demographics.

Age	Frequency	% Share
Social Sciences	38	10
Natural Sciences	46	13
Engineering	152	41
Other etc	113	31
Total	368	100

The study applies the frequency distribution techniques in the initial phase to check about the respondents view against each statement. Section 1, Table 5 covers the statements related to digital information access. Regarding the regular access to digital resources, 165 respondents are strongly agreeing and 124 are agree, whereas only a fraction of the respondents (27 respondents) were disagreed with it. There is a well diversity of the library resource as overall, 328 respondents are showing their agreed point overall into this matter. Moreover, whether the digital library platform is user friendly or not, again, the study observes majority respondents are showing positive feedback. The fourth statement “Enhanced Research Abilities” where 193 respondents are agreeing and 61 are strongly agree. The last statement is covering the dealing of research choices, showing that out of 368, 258 respondents are strongly agreeing for the influence of the digital resources on their research choices.

Table 5: Section 1: Digital Information Access (DIA).

Questions	1 (Strongly Disagree)	2 (Disagree)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Agree)	5 (Strongly Agree)
• I regularly access digital resources (e-books, journals, databases) through the university library platform.	27	41	11	124	165
• The digital resources available through the library are diverse and cover a wide range of topics.	8	19	13	202	126
• I find the digital library platform user-friendly and easy to navigate.	22	42	92	108	104
• Access to digital information has enhanced my ability to conduct research for academic purposes.	5	27	82	193	61
• The availability of digital resources influences my choice of research topics and areas of study.	25	15	4	66	258

The same distribution as covered in Table 5 is in Figure 2 where in call the categories, the maximum

responses are related to either four or fifth points of the given scale.

Figure 2: Digital Information Access (Bar charts of the Responses as captured).

Section two in the questionnaire deals with the library platforms and related statements. The same has been given in Table 6. First statement means the “the

access to resources for learning purpose” and it shows a diversified opinion. Out of 368, 169 are agreed and 151 are strongly agree for the statement that there is an

access to resources for learning objective by library platform. The next statement has a key objective to explore “exploration of diverse perspectives” and again the study gets highest responses on 4th and 5th point. Moreover, the study further accesses the respondents view about the “influence on global

thinking”. This statement also presents majority of the feedback for the agreed point.

The similar distribution reflects by using the Figure 3. Similar to the Figure 2, higher numbers of responses are captured by each fourth and fifth point.

Table 6: Section 2: Library Platforms (LIP).

Question	1 (Strongly Disagree)	2 (Disagree)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Agree)	5 (Strongly Agree)
• The library platform provides easy access to various resources that support my learning and academic growth.	22	18	8	169	151
• I have used the library’s digital resources to explore different cultural, philosophical, or ideological perspectives.	37	11	19	98	203
• The library’s digital resources have influenced the way I think about global issues and diverse perspectives.	57	23	45	164	79

Figure 3: Library Platforms (Bar Charts of the Responses as Captured).

Section 3 deals with the worldwide formation of the students. The following five categories were explored and described in Table 7.

- Expanded Understanding of Cultures: for this statement, 92 respondents agreed and 158 are strongly agreed, therefore, highly favouring the expanded understanding of the cultures by using the digital resources.
- Shaping Personal Beliefs and Values: for this statement in the questionnaire, 169 are agreed and 79 are strongly agree where the personal beliefs and values are upgraded by the digital resources.
- Development of Open-Mindedness: again, for this statement, respondents are highly obliging

that through library platforms, they become open-minded.

- Encouragement to Reflect on Views: this statement is also showing a good sense of understanding among the students, and their views are aligned with it.
- Preparation for a Global Society: the library digital resources are giving more global connection with the diverse society, and this is consistent in the current study analysis of frequency distribution.

The distribution of students in Section 3 in different frequencies is also covered in Diagram named Figure 4.

Table 7: Section 3: Student Worldview Formation (SWF).

Question	1 (Strongly Disagree)	2 (Disagree)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Agree)	5 (Strongly Agree)
• The digital resources I access through the library have expanded my understanding of different cultures and societies.	15	61	42	92	158
• My exposure to various global perspectives through digital resources has shaped my personal beliefs and values.	63	25	32	169	79
• Accessing a variety of ideologies through the library platform has helped me become more open-minded.	82	33	51	111	91
• The digital resources have encouraged me to question and reflect on my existing views and assumptions.	55	61	82	123	47
• I feel that using the library’s digital resources has prepared me to work in a more globally connected and diverse society.	32	15	55	124	142

Figure 4: Student Worldview Formation (Bar charts of the Responses as captured).

Section 4, Table 8 represents the ideological education, and three statements are linked to it. The statements cover the following key points:

- i. Understanding Political and Social Ideologies
As per political understanding and social ideologies of the students which is the first statement in ideological education, 123 students are agreed and 57 are strongly agreed to get this point.
Conversely, 124 are not agreed at all with such claims and 32 are rejected it while disagreeing with it.
- ii. Shaping Views on Social Justice and Equality

Another theme captured under ideological education is shaping views about social justice and quality. Again, the responses are mixed, yet 141 are strongly agree and 91 are disagree to it.

- iii. Challenging Ideologies and Promoting Critical Thinking

This is the last theme under section 4, and overall, 244 respondents are in favouring to it. This represents overall more than 66% of the participants with such agreement out of 368. Figure 5 shows out section 4’s distribution using bar charts.

Table 8: Section 4: Ideological Education.

Question	1 (Strongly Disagree)	2 (Disagree)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Agree)	5 (Strongly Agree)
• The use of digital resources in my education helps me understand various political, philosophical, and social ideologies.	124	32	32	123	57
• The digital resources have shaped my understanding of social justice and equality.	63	91	44	29	141
• I feel that the library’s digital resources challenge my previous ideologies and promote critical thinking.	12	38	74	127	117

Figure 5: Ideological Education (Bar charts of the Responses as captured).

Path Analysis

Here the researchers have conducted the path analysis. The first three paths are showing the impact of DIA on LIP, DIA on SWF and IDE on SWF. Additionally, the fourth path is dealing with the LIP and SWF.

The second last path is showing interaction term of IDE and DIA towards SWF. The last path is showing the mediating role of LIP between DIA and SWF. The closer look for each of the path is given in the following details below Table 9:

Table 9: Path Analysis

Details	Sample Coefficients	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
DIA -> LIP	0.619	0.090	6.897	0.000
DIA -> SWF	0.159	0.019	8.369	0.000
IDE -> SWF	0.450	0.093	4.824	0.000
LIP -> SWF	0.406	0.081	4.998	0.000
IDE x DIA -> SWF	0.083	0.036	2.326	0.020
DIA -> LIP -> SWF	0.251	0.059	4.249	0.000

Note: Digital Information Access (DIA), Independent Variable (IV), Library Platforms (LIP), Mediator Variable, Student Worldview Formation (SWF), Dependent Variable (DV), Ideological Education (IDE), Moderator Variable

Digital Information Access Fuels Library Platform Engagement

The impact of digital information access on the usage of Library Platforms is substantial, with a positive coefficient of 0.619 and a t-statistic of 6.897. This relationship signifies that when students have greater access to digital resources, they tend to utilize the library platforms more effectively.

This is confirmed through the t-value and p-value as they reflected in Table above.

Digital Information Access Shapes Students' Worldview

A key finding is that DIA significantly contributes to the student worldview formation, with a coefficient of 0.159. A better digital information access is shaping the student worldview formation.

Ideological Education Influences Students' Perspectives

Ideological Education plays a pivotal role in shaping SWF, with a coefficient of 0.450 and a t-statistic of 4.824. This result indicates that the knowledge students gain from various political, philosophical, and social ideologies significantly impacts their worldview. In this context, IDE acts as a foundation for fostering critical thinking and understanding complex global issues, ultimately influencing how students see themselves in the world.

Library Platforms Enhance Worldview Formation

The positive relationship between LIP and SWF highlights the power of accessible, diverse resources in shaping students' worldviews. With a coefficient of 0.406 and a t-statistic of 4.998, it is clear that when students engage with resources on library platforms, they develop a deeper understanding of diverse perspectives. The ability to access a wide range of global knowledge strengthens their ability to critically analyze cultural, social, and ideological narratives.

Synergistic Effect: Ideological Education and Digital Access

The interaction between Ideological Education and Digital Information Access produces a notable enhancement in SWF, with a coefficient of 0.083 and a t-statistic of 2.326. This interaction shows that the combined influence of digital access and ideological education creates a more profound impact on worldview formation. When students have access to both digital resources and diverse ideological perspectives, they are better equipped to develop a multifaceted understanding of the world.

Indirect Path: Digital Access Through Library Platforms

The indirect effect of DIA on SWF through LIP is equally significant, with a coefficient of 0.251. This path illustrates how digital information access enhances the use of library platforms, which, in turn, supports the formation of a student's worldview. As students engage more with digital resources through library platforms, they gain exposure to global knowledge that nurtures a more inclusive and comprehensive perspective.

Conclusion and Policy Formulation

This research is a unique contribution to the domain of Ideological Education through digital information and library platforms. An exceptional research effort has been carried out which indeed a major contribution in the domain of the student worldview formation. The results uses both the frequency distribution and path analysis. The specific path analysis show that DIA is shaping the library platforms usage and enhancing Student worldview

formation. Ideological Education (IDE) amplifies this effect, contributing significantly to students' worldview development. The mediation role of LIP illustrates how access to diverse digital resources fosters broader cultural and ideological understanding. Furthermore, the interaction between DIA and IDE demonstrates a combined effect that strengthens worldview formation. These results highlight the importance of integrating digital tools with ideological education to cultivate well-rounded, globally conscious students. The short and comprehensive policies to be implemented are here as follows:

- The relevant administration should expand the reach of digital resources to ensure equitable access, particularly in underfunded educational institutions.
- The university administration is recommended to incorporate diverse ideological perspectives into curricula to foster critical thinking and broader worldviews among students.
- They must invest in improving the user interface and accessibility of library platforms to maximize student engagement with digital resources.
- University management should encourage the integration of digital tools in interdisciplinary teaching, enabling students to draw connections across various fields of study.
- The management should provide continuous training for educators to enhance their proficiency in utilizing digital resources, thereby improving teaching outcomes and student engagement.

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